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Welcome to our December 2021 newsletter

Despite much fatigue with virtual participation at meetings and events, our second fully virtual and self-paced summer school which ran Sept-Nov was well attended - read on to hear from the participants themselves. We bring you news of the forthcoming Data Schools Forum and how to get involved in the Alumni Working Group. If you were unable to attend the Alumni Series webinar on *afrimapr - R building blocks and a community for mapping African data*, we have a full report from the presenters, Anelda van der Walt and Andy South. Of course, don't miss our regular alumni profiles, this edition with Anup Das from India and Iris Diana Uy from the Philippines, and our instructor profile is Stephen Diggs, who teaches practical sessions on RDM at the schools. Do you know how our alumni interactive map was created? Read on, Rob Quick tells us all about its origin and how it works. Finally, we have an introduction to GOSC, the Global Open Science Cloud, for those of you who are not yet familiar with this initiative aimed at cooperation, alignment and interoperability among open science initiatives.

We hope you enjoy reading the newsletter and, for those of you taking time away from all things virtual, on behalf of the Data Schools co-chairs, I wish you an enjoyable break and a very peaceful new year.

Bridget Walker

AN IoT VIRTUAL MEETING, TRIESTE, ITALY SEPTEMBER 2021

The 2021 summer school took place entirely online and was self-paced from 6th September to 19th November. 82 early career researchers attended from 34 countries. We have received much positive feedback and are very pleased to share this with you.

The Data Science Summer School was both a challenging and exciting experience for me. As someone who is not from the computer science background, programming was the major challenge and as an online course, sometimes it was difficult to catch up. It was a good learning experience and I am happy about the areas I mastered during the summer school. I will continue practising until I master all the concepts. Thank you.

Josiline Chigwada, Zimbabwe

The summer school experience was my first leap into Data Science. I have had prior experience in some Analytical software like SPSS but little did I know that was just a tip of the iceberg. Now I know the basics of Machine learning, and coding and combining these resources in data analysis and management.

The program has changed my perspective of research, now I know about Open and fair research, Creative commons, Orcid and other platforms that aid research dissemination and archiving.

I can go on and on and it would seem endless. I am grateful for this platform because it Opened a great opportunity for me. Thank you to all the instructors, facilitators and organisations that financially invested in this program.

Olagunja Sola, Nigeria

As a second-year Ph.D. student, I am ever grateful to the organisers and teachers (or volunteers) for the manner in which we were guided through the courses. The knowledge gained in data analysis and machine learning in addition to exposure to various online platforms including virtual machines will ease my Ph.D. research work despite a large amount of dataset expected to be analysed. The attitude of the teachers and other contributors to participants and their response to our questions is highly commendable. I sincerely thank all of you.

Amadi Brians, Brazil

I'm forever grateful for what this school has offered me. I had never coded in R but thanks to this summer school I can now do a lot of things in R. Instructional videos were very informative and purposeful.

Thanks to this Summer School, I can apply this in my field of Geoscience.

Eric Dominic Forson, Ghana

that could meet my research needs. Honestly, the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School was absolutely amazing and a perfect one for all competency levels. The school provided me a solid foundation and improved my confidence in research data analysis and data curation using various software. I found the learning platform interesting, and the teacher's creativity made learning simple, enjoyable, and exciting.

Lanre Anthony Gbadegesin, China

CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School by ICTP was challenging and fascinating at the same time. I personally feel that the school was very well organized despite being offered virtually. I was literally amazed seeing the efforts and hard work that each teacher did put into this course. They were smart, experts in their respective topics and gave their best to make us learn. Also, to keep the class interesting and focused they insisted us to frequently ask questions every now and then. truth be told, I really enjoyed every minute of it.

Akash Chauhan, India

I was a helper in the school this year. I wanted to leave a comment about the school. The CODATA-RDA summer school is a great opportunity to learn about data management and meet people who are working in exciting research. I've had the honor to participate in the school several years and it is great to see that both in person and virtually, the impact of the school is very positive.

José López, France

My heartfelt appreciation to the organizers and facilitators of CODATA-RDA Summer School 2021. It was a great experience for me learning some Data Science skills for the first time. Thank you all for the enlightenment.

Justina Achuka, Nigeria

When I applied to the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School I only expected to improve my R skills, learn about GitHub and maybe know people working with biological data. My expectations were widely met. I learned a lot of new things in R and also I learned about new topics I never had thought (like BASH, openData, FAIR Data, and data security). All the teachers were amazing and they did everything they could to make us feel comfortable with the virtual mode. I enjoyed the last week of Summer School a lot and I think that it was very useful for anybody who is starting in Science in general. It was an incredible experience and highly recommended.

Elizabeth Cattaneo, Argentina

Abraham Lincoln once said, "The best way to predict the future is to create it." And for me, the story of the CODATA RDA Research Data Science Summer School organized by ICTP was one such postcard in my life which has a story of beginnings, learnings & evolution. With an extremely committed & helpful

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engage with experts and diverse groups. And most importantly, contributing your time & resources to strengthen my skills, ideas, cognizance, and research!

Rashmii Sri, India

This CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School has been very interesting to start with friendly, hard working and intelligent people. The knowledge obtained from this summer school will be very helpful to hone the academic and research career. Thank you so much for providing me the opportunity to be a part of this school.

Madhavi Parajuli, Nepal

I study physics and your university is one of the best universities in the world in this field. By participating in this course, I was able to get acquainted with a new and powerful programming language and participate in my research and studies, and I am trying to develop my abilities in this program.

Mehdii Lotfi, Iran

Data Schools Forum

The Data Schools Forum, hosted on our [website](#) will soon be going live.

If you would like to be registered on the forum and you haven't yet sent us your confirmation please do so at dataschools@codata.org.

The Forum is the place where you will be able to:

- raise questions
- promote events
- find alumni in your area

The main objective of the Forum is to offer a platform where ideas can be exchanged, questions can be raised and events can be promoted. Of course, it's a great place to also find other alumni in your area.

The Forum is all about getting researchers, engineers, and students to meet, exchange and acquire new scientific and technical skills to help them overcome both current and future unresolved issues. It has a variety of different topic areas but if the right one doesn't exist we can set it up.

The Forum will be monitored by a small editorial team of volunteers who will respond to any questions or direct them to the Data Schools

Remember - let us know if you would like to be registered on the forum - dataschools@codata.org.

Alumni Working Group

Do you want to use your communication, organisation and writing skills? Why not get involved in the Alumni Working Group? We're looking for volunteers who can help organise the Alumni Webinar Series, put together content for the newsletter, work on new mentorship and translation projects and start an initiative of alumni video presentations to strengthen the alumni network. If you are able to commit some time and effort, we'd love to hear from you, just let us know - dataschools@codata.org.

Alumni Webinar Series

There have been a series of webinars held this year, jointly hosted by the [CODATA Connect initiative](#) and the CODATA-RDA Schools of research Data Science Alumni Group. The following webinar took place in June.

afrimapr - R building blocks and a community for mapping African data

Authors: Anelda van der Walt, Andy South

Data scientist and analyst roles are increasing across the globe, including in Africa, in government, academia, non profits, humanitarian organisations, and industry.. Communities like R and Python User Groups, RLadies, Women in GIS, and others provide opportunities for data scientists to learn, share, discuss, and grow together. In Africa alone the RLadies movement has over 4'000 members. These analysts play critical roles in providing decision makers with essential information distilled from open and proprietary data. Information is presented in the form of reports, dashboards, plots, and often maps.

Despite this proliferation of analysts, the growth of open science and open data, and innovation around tools for data analysis and visualisation, making data-driven maps can still be remarkably complicated. It really doesn't need to be.

[afrimapr's](#) vision is to:

- create learning material to support human capacity development; and
- support the development of a community of practice in Africa around map making in R.

The project kicked off in 2020 through funding from the Wellcome Trust Open Research Fund. The [Open Research Fund](#) aimed to support researchers “to develop and test incentives for making health research more open, accessible and reusable”. In 2021 afrimapr received follow-up funding through [Wellcome Trust Data for Science and Health](#).

Interestingly, the project leads met during the first CODATA-RDA School for Research Data Science hosted in Trieste in 2016. Little did we know then, that 4 years later we were going to be collaborating on this exciting project!

Data & Code

All code developed by the afrimapr community is available on Github, an open platform enabling code sharing, collaboration, and version control. Code is published under open licenses to facilitate broad and easy re-use, modification and adoption.

In 2020 and 2021 a number of packages were developed focusing on making open data more accessible.

The team published a peer-reviewed article focusing on [open health facility data in Africa](#). An [interactive web application](#) allows users to compare existing open health facility data sets as seen in the image below.

Other packages and interactive web applications can be viewed on the [afrimapr website](#).

Supported tutorial in French and English

The afrimapr team & collaborators developed and delivered a 4-hour supported tutorial for the useR!2021 conference. The tutorial was offered in two separate

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to re-use the useR! tutorial, the learning materials were subsequently adapted slightly to fit a broader audience and are now available (along with instructions for use) on the afrimapr Github repository at <https://github.com/afrimapr/r-maps-tutorial-fr-eng>.

Community

Most importantly, afrimapr aims to collaborate and co-create with analysts and data scientists in Africa. A [monthly community meetup](#) allows community members to meet each other and share code, ideas, challenges, and opportunities.

afrimapr also joined forces with the global [R for Data Science Online Learning Community](#) to help African data scientists and analysts embed themselves in the larger R community for continued support, collaboration, and networking. afrimapr hosts a channel, #chat-africa_maps on the R4DS Slack workspace and anyone interested is welcome to join!

Anyone interested in learning more or joining our community can subscribe to the [afrimapr Google Group](#) for updates about events, activities, and resources.

Finally, the [afrimapr Twitter account](#) is a great place to learn more about mapping events, resources, and training from around the globe. We're also happy to retweet your work on African mapping in R! Let us know when you've got something to share.

Alumni Profile

Anup Das

I, Dr. Anup Kumar Das, am a Senior Documentation Officer (academic researcher, information and data science professional) working with the Centre for Studies in Science Policy at Jawaharlal Nehru University, India, since January 2007. I am an alumnus of the CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science, and participated in the CODATA International Training Workshop in Open Data for Better Science, in Beijing, China in 2017. Subsequently I attended the virtual CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science in September 2020. My participation in CODATA-RDA research data science schools has helped me in taking up different professional roles both nationally and at the community level. I became a core team member of *CODATA Connect – Early Career and Alumni Network* since 2019; and *CODATA India National Working Group* since 2021. I have also been an individual member of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) since 2017. I regularly get relevant information and announcements from the *CODATA Training and Careers List* <data_science_training@lists.codata.org> that have enriched my understanding on research data science and participation in relevant capacity development events. I also share many relevant posts to this e-forum, particularly which are related to the Global South. I serve as a Joint Convener of 'Open Access India' – an advocacy group to promote open access, open research data, open science, and open educational resources. I was associated as an Information Specialist/Consultant with UNESCO New Delhi in 2006, later as a Consultant with the Commonwealth of Learning (COL). I have written two books: "Open Access to Knowledge and Information: Scholarly Literature and Digital Library Initiatives – the South Asian Scenario" (UNESCO,

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Curricula for Researchers and Library Schools (UNESCO, 2015). My research interests revolve around open science, open access, open research data, digital inclusion, information policies, knowledge societies, and scientometrics. I am an Editor-cum-Book Review Editor of the *Journal of Scientometric Research* (JSCIRES), and an Associate Editor of the *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development* (AJSTID). As the Principal Investigator, I completed a DST India-funded research project titled “A Comparative Study of India’s Research Performance in Scientific and Technological Areas of Clean Energy and Water (2006-17): A Scientometric Analysis”. As the HEIRRI collaborator, I was responsible for pilot testing of the HEIRRI Training Modules “Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in Higher Education Institutions” in India, developed by HEIRRI Project, GUNi – Global University Network for Innovation, 2017-18. I was awarded PhD from Jadavpur University, India, in 2009. I am very keen to engage with data science professionals, and early career researchers from the Global South, particularly for the implementation of *FAIR Data Principles*, and *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science* at the institutional, national and funders' levels. My list of publications and professional engagements can be found on my website: <http://www.anupkumardas.blogspot.com>. I can be contacted at [anup_csp\[@\]jnu.ac.in](mailto:anup_csp[@]jnu.ac.in). ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-9490-7938>.

Alumni Profile

Iris Diana Uy

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bioinformatician from the Philippines. After finishing my bachelor's degree in molecular biology and biotechnology, I joined the National Institutes of Health in Manila, where I studied cancer genetics within the Filipino population. I later pursued my masters in Marine Biotechnology at the Marine Science Institute (MSI) of the University of the Philippines. In the same institute, I had the opportunity to work as a researcher in several omics projects. Applications of these studies range from supporting sustainable mariculture and marine conservation efforts, to marine bioprospecting for drug development. I later joined the Philippine Genome Center (PGC) as part of the pilot team of the PGC's Core Facility for Bioinformatics. In this capacity, I assisted several local research projects in their bioinformatics analyses. I also helped develop service protocols and modules for bioinformatics trainings--all of which are still at the centre of the facility's activities in service of Filipino researchers. I was also a research bioinformatician for the International Cooperative Biodiversity Groups (ICBG) program in MSI and the University of Utah. When I had the opportunity, I mentored for Women Who Code (Manila).

As a researcher and a core facility bioinformatician, I recognized the trade-offs of big data in the conduct of rigorous yet reproducible research. In 2019, I participated in the CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Summer School and Advanced Workshop on Bioinformatics at the ICTP in Trieste, Italy. At the school, I learned not only methods for big data analysis, but also frameworks and tools that promote findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data for research. The school has equipped me to take more intentional and concrete steps towards reproducible big data research.

In January 2022, I will happily join the European Molecular Biology Laboratories - European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI), an international organisation that develops tools and databases that researchers can use to leverage the vast amount of biological data in the world for science that benefits humanity. EMBL-EBI is also an advocate of open science and the FAIR data principles for scientific research. The CODATA-RDA school has been instrumental in preparing me to take this next phase of my career.

Data Schools Alumni Interactive World Map

This [interactive world map](#) was created as a graduate visualisation project by students at Indiana University-Purdue University Indianapolis. The goal of the map was to visualise alumni and provide contact information to community members of past lecturers, helpers, and participants for future events and collaborations.

[7O552jiHY/editbuilt](#) and uses the D3 (Data-Driven Documents) JavaScript library from <https://d3js.org> to perform visualisation tasks. The base map is an open source geoJSON D3 world map template (<http://techslides.com/d3-map-starter-kit>) that allows panning and zooming.

A heatmap colour scheme was chosen to be colour-blind friendly and show participant distribution. Site labels and years were also added to mark locations and years of each event.

The map has two interactive functionalities based on mousing over components and clicking components of the visualisation.

Mousing over the map will show the number of attendees that are 1) currently at institutions in that country and 2) originating from that country. You can also mouse over the donut graphs at the bottom of the map to get the percentages of participants based on gender, field of study, city of the first school they attended, and year of the first school they attended.

Clicking on a country or a section in the donut graphs will list the names and contacts of those represented by that population in the table below the graphs.

Please feel free to contact Rob Quick rquick@iu.edu with any questions.

Instructor Profile

Stephen Diggs

I am Steve Diggs, Technical Director of the Hydrographic Data Office at Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO). Scripps is at my alma mater, UC San Diego, located in sunny Southern California. SIO is where I became an engineer and data analyst while finishing my degree. Because SIO is really an interdisciplinary Earth Sciences Institution, I've been able to work with Marine

UCSD is also where I became an instructor for its Extended Studies Program, where I taught operating systems internals and comparative programming languages just as Unix was being accepted in the corporate world. At the time Linux was just a rumor, the internet was still experimental and no one that I knew personally had programmed in Python.

My RDA instructor journey started in 2017, a year after SciDataCon in Denver. I was rotating off RDA's Technical Advisory board and thought that engaging through the new RDA/CODATA Summer Schools would keep me out of trouble. After conversations with Sarah Jones, Rob Quick, and Simon Hodson, they thought that Sarah and I would make a good team teaching both the theory as well as practical aspects of Research Data Management (RDM).

My first school was the 2017 Sao Paulo Schools in December 2017. I based my hands-on practical module on Sarah's conceptual introduction. I get tired of the sound of my own voice after about 30 minutes, so challenging the students to find data based on a collection of published papers seemed to be just the thing to keep the group engaged after a long week of lecture-based learning. I have been fortunate to be able to continually develop and teach this module in Trieste, Costa Rica, and now, online.

Even though we have been challenged with delivering this content virtually, I look forward to returning to in-person instruction and reconnecting with students and colleagues in 2022!

The Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) Initiative

The major global scientific and human challenges of the 21st century (including COVID-19 and future pandemics, anthropogenic climate change, sustainable development, and disaster risk reduction) can only be addressed through cross-domain research that seeks to understand complex systems through machine-assisted analysis at scale. The digital revolution can accelerate such research by means of the Open Science paradigm comprising the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Principles, rigorous scientific transparency, and intelligent openness. A number of governments and research funders have adopted policies promoting or requiring Open Science and the FAIR Principles. UNESCO has adopted [recommendations on Open Science](#).

The Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) initiative aims to encourage cooperation, and ultimately alignment and interoperability, between these and

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paragraph are likely to be significant: the benefits will be even greater if alignment can be achieved on a global scale.

With the aim of encouraging cooperation, and ultimately alignment and interoperability, among these and similar endeavours, the Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) initiative will go forward as an integral part of the [ISC CODATA Decadal Program 'Making Data Work for Cross Domain Grand Challenges'](#).

The vision for a global coordinating activity emerged from a number of discussions, including those at the [2019 CODATA Conference in Beijing](#), and the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) has granted seed funding for CNIC to help launch the initiative. A series of subsequent meetings and workshops, including the [EGI, CNIC, and CODATA GOSC Workshop](#), and the [GOSC Panel and GOSC Parallel Session](#) during the [International FAIR Convergence Symposium 2020](#), have helped validate and enrich the GOSC concept.

A number of working groups have been set up to address the challenges associated with developing this initiative. Though these are very much initial steps, the vision of enabling such a global level of cooperation has started.

Have you enjoyed reading the newsletter? Do you have ideas for future editions? Get involved in the Alumni WG and be part of a volunteer editorial team! Just email us at dataschools@codata.org

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